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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE SIBYL'S CAVE: WHAT WE KNOW¹

The mystery of Mount Sibyl in Italy is an ancient one, an enigma which is still unsolved. The mountain raises its peak between Umbria and Marche. The cave on the mountain-top has been visited for centuries by men from all over Europe in search of the legendary subterranean realm of the Sibyl of the Apennines. A quest that definitely is not over.

Throughout the centuries, the cave on the top of Mount Sibyl has been the target of manifold efforts to break into its secret meanders. Entrance was not an easy matter, because the cave had been sealed by the order of the Popes. As many ancient writers report, the town of Norcia was forced to close the entrance to the cave lest enchanters and necromancers gain access to the inner rooms "to stage their abominable rituals". In "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", Antoine de La Sale narrates that in the fourteenth century Pope Urban commanded that the path leading to Mount Sibyl's crown be destroyed, and "the entrance to the cave sealed", as magicians from all over Europe were used to attain the Sibyl's peak to consecrate their spellbooks to the powers of darkness.

This article summarises part of the information available on the eerie cave, as drawn from a number of different sources. A travel into mystery that still continues in our present days.

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1. A vivid description of Mount Sibyl: impressions by Fernand Desonay

Belgian philologist Fernand Desonay was so enamoured of the Apennine Sibyl's legend that he travelled many times to Mount Sibyl. The passionate words he wrote about his journeys fully show the immense attractiveness of the ancient tale centered on this famous peak:

«On August, 26th 1929 I was able to consider, from the back of a small brown donkey, the mists swirling on the mountain-sides of the Apennines... The vision of those mountains seizes your heart; the silence around, it utterly petrifies your soul. You see Mount Vettore at last, with the lake of Pilatus! Up there, the ancestral worship and tales have their roots!... We are setting off in search of a mystery. [...] I have in my pocket the work by Antoine de La Sale; for I intend to check all the geographical information provided in the Chantilly manuscript. After much effort, we have reached the base of the “crown”. La Sale says that it's a cliff some fifteen feet high, “cut in the mount along the whole circumference”. It's right. When seen from a distance, this crown may truly appear as a fortress, or a temple. Sure enough, the vista is so picturesque; and it can hardly be reckoned it is just a natural feature: such a large bulk of rock crushing the mountain-top and shaped as a dome must have striken the mind's eye.»

Fig. 1 - Mount Sibyl, the mountain raising its crowned peak in Italy, between Marche and Umbria

[in the original French wording: «Le 26 août 1929, je pouvais contempler, du haut de l'échine d'un petit âne brun, les jeux de la 'nebbia' sur les pentes de l'Apennin... [...] L'aspect de ces montagnes vous serre le coeur; le silence d'alentour, on dirait qu'il vous paralyse. Voilà donc le Vettore, avec le lac de Pilate! C'est là-haut qu'ont surgi les cultes antiques et les légendes!... Nous partirons à la découverte du mystère. [...] J'ai dans ma poche le texte d'Antoine de La Sale; car je veux contrôler toutes les indications topographiques du manuscrit de Chantilly. Après de longs efforts, nous sommes arrivés au pied de la "couronne". La Sale dit qu'il s'agit d'une roche haute de cinq mètres environ, "taillée dans la montagne sur tout le pourtour". C'est exact. Vue de loin, cette couronne peut donner l'impression d'une forteresse, voire d'un temple. Certes, tout ceci est fort caractéristique; et l'on ne peut croire qu'il s'agisse d'une formation naturelle: pareille masse qui écrase la montagne en forme de coupole a dû frapper l'imagination.»]

Fernand Desonay had a special dream about Mount Sibyl. He left precious, perfectly beautiful words on his dream, which I use to quote in my presentation sessions on the Sibyl's legend. I have recently found the original French wording, which is contained in his article "Les sources italiennes de la légende de Tannhäuser":

«Je songe à la Sibylle. Mon regard va, va... Il escalade les rampes des montagnes, franchit les précipices... Sous la couronne de rochers, voici la déesse, - c'est elle! - inspiratrice nostalgique du plus beau des songes humains...»

«I am dreaming of the Sibyl... My eyes travel up and further up... My gaze climbs the crests, jumps across the ravines... Beneath the crown of stone, there I see the goddess - there she is! - she, who inspires my longing for the most ravishing among human dreams...».

Fig. 2 - Mount Sibyl and the imaginative words by Fernand Desonay

2. The cave in Roman times

In present days no one can tell what the Sibyl's cave looked like in antiquity.

For certain, on the peak of Mount Sibyl a cavern opened its gloomy jaws providing an access to the mount's internal bowels. Was that a special worship place dedicated to some ancient mother-god? Researchers think it might have been a rocky temple, with carved columns and inscriptions bearing mention of goddess Cybele, but no evidence has ever been found.

What was to be found in the Sibyl's cave in Roman times? After climbing the steep mountain-slope, the visitor would reach the Sibyl's peak, an isolated place of worship situated at an elevation of more than 7,000 feet. Nothing but a frosty wind and the remote stars above would accompany the believer. There, the dark cave, possibly with carved lintels and pillars, would be waiting for men to enter its recesses. Inside the cave, no one can

tell what was to be encountered: an altar, a ritual fire, a prophesying oracle. A Sibyl, perhaps, like the one of Delphi, in Greece: «Sibyl», Plutarch wrote in his *De Pythiae Oraculis*, «who speaks mournful words with delirious lips».

3. A visit to the Sibyl dating to 1420

In 1420, a French gentleman, Antoine de La Sale, ascended Mount Sibyl. Why had he come from so distant a country to climb a peak hidden in the middle of the Apennine range in Italy? Six hundred years ago, the mount had already achieved its uncanny renown: Mr. de La Sale had been told that Mount Sibyl was the secret abode of a prophetess and priestess, the Apennine Sibyl.

A cave was on the top of the mount: it was the gateway to a subterranean kingdom, buried within the very core of the cliff. A maze of caverns and dark halls would provide access to a wonderful underground realm: fine palaces and damsels and gold were concealed under the rock.

He heard of all that. And he decided to go. And make his personal exploration into the matter.

A well-known route to Mount Sibyl leads to the cliff from the small hamlet of Montemonaco. That's the same route that Antoine de La Sale trod with horses and a retinue of peasants in 1420 when he climbed the mountain-side to visit the magical cave. A tortuous road goes up the flank of Mount Sibyl, with lots of bends and twists, up to the "Sibyl's Refuge", a resting place for hikers and bikers. From there on, the trail ascends the grassy mountain-side until it reaches the high crests leading straight to the Sibyl's peak.

As one walks the rocky ridges, looking down at the bottomless ravines standing on both sides, one remembers the words written by de La Sale centuries ago: «ne fault point qu'il face vent», you must hope for the wind not to blow too angrily, not to be flung into the abysses which present to your sight as open jaws.

Antoine de La Sale handed down to us a quite remarkable drawing: the Sibillini Range is portrayed with all its fascinating elements, the same who attracted travellers from centuries from all across Europe.

Fig. 3 - Mount Sibyl and the Sibillini Range as shown in the drawing included in the 1527 printed edition of “La Salade” by Antoine de La Sale

On the left side of the picture, a large mountain stands with a lake on its top: it's the “The Lake of the Sibyl” (“Le Lac de la Sibille” in the French caption), also known today as the Lake of Pilatus. On the right side is Mount Sibyl (“Le mont de la Sibille”), with its lofty crown (“la couronne du mont”) and featuring a gloomy hole on the very peak: it is the Sibyl's cave, or “the entrance to the cavern” (“l'entrée de la cave”). In the middle, the valley where the small hamlet of Foce (“Fogia”) guards the trail to the lake.

This is the map drawn by Antoine de La Sale, the French gentleman who visited Mount Sibyl on May 18th 1420 and reported his journey in a famous work, “Le Paradis de la Reine Sibylle”. This version of the map is contained in a printed edition of his book, published in Paris in 1527.

The map is another remarkable instance of the widespread renown which the Sibillini Range enjoyed in past centuries among foreign countries all over Europe. The sinister lake with its demons, the dark cave which was the abode of a Sibyl were set in a unique, extraordinary mix of picturesque, hair-raising landscape and thrilling traditional lore: a combination that would push scores of noblemen, knights, adventurers and treasure hunters as far as this remote region of mountains and precipices.

Fig. 4 - Antoine de La Sale's exploration of the Sibyl's cave in 1420 as depicted in a manuscript preserved in Chantilly (France)

After getting to the mountain-top, Antoine de La Sale actually entered the cave. And he wrote an account of what he could see in the outer subterranean chamber. By the glow of his torchlight, Antoine de La Sale - himself a foreigner in Italy - noted a number of "carved inscriptions": they were names of foreigners as well, "Hans Wan Banborg", "Thomin Le Pons" and others.

Why people from far-off countries had come to Italy as far as that remote mountain and its cave? What secret was concealed under the huge mass of rock making up the mountain-top?

What they all were looking for? And why people are still coming to the Sibyl's peak in our present day?

An enigma is concealed under that mountain. And the enigma is still present today: in the same spot as several centuries ago.

4. The cave sealed

Throughout the centuries, the cave on the top of Mount Sibyl has been the target of manifold efforts to break into its secret meanders.

For centuries its fame had run across Europe, so much so that scores of undesired travellers used to flock to Italy from Germany and other northern European countries to visit the cavern.

They were not mere tourists. They were wizards and sorcerers coming from their respective homelands to consecrate their spellbooks and "to stage their abominable rituals", as reported in 1650 by Father Fortunato Ciucci, a local scholar and historian. The town of Norcia, under whose rule the cavern rested at that time, "was then compelled to seal the entrance to the alleged Sibyl, as it is still sealed today". All that occurred in the seventeenth century, but the attempts at breaking into the cavern and meet the fabulous Sibyl weren't over at all.

So entrance was not an easy matter. Even in "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", Antoine de La Sale narrates that in the fourteenth century Pope Urban commanded that the path leading to Mount Sibyl's crown be destroyed, and "the entrance to the cave sealed", as magicians from all over Europe were used to attain the Sibyl's peak to consecrate their spellbooks to the powers of darkness.

5. *The summoning of the clouds*

Explorations at the Sibyl's cavern have never been a plain task, both in past centuries and in our present times.

Anyone who had ever made an attempt at reaching the Sibyl's mountain-top knows well that the legendary prophetess has many ways to prevent undesired visitors from getting to her cliff: suddenly, rolling clouds extend through the sky carried by a cold, damp wind, and heavy lashes of rain start hitting the wayfarer's face: this is the signal that we must go back, and quickly, for the Apennine Sibyl bids no welcome.

Giovanni Battista Lalli, a poet from Norcia who lived in the seventeenth century, had a first-hand experience of this same occurrence, as he himself wrote in his poem “Ruined Jerusalem”:

«And if anyone unwelcomed dares to draw too near, and she chooses to deny herself to him, in various manners he repels him from his venturesome design. Sometimes she fills the sky with gloomy clouds carrying the rain, so that a horrible storm comes to life; sometimes with a mortal threat, any mercy dispelled, she unleashes the savage beasts against the wayfarer.»

Fig. 5 - Vista from the cliff of Mount Sibyl with rapidly flowing clouds

[in the original Italian text:
E se quivi appressarsi alcun s'accinge,
Ch'à lei no piaccia, e d'introdur no'l degna;
Con diverse maniere il risospinge
Da quell'impresa, che tentar disegna.
D'atre, e gravide nubi hor l'aria cinge,
Che ria tempesta à partorir ne vegna;
Hor minacciosa, ogni pietà sbandita,
Contro di quel l'horrende belve irrita.]

*6. A seventeenth-century poet from Norcia meets the Apennine Sibyl:
Giovanni Battista Lalli*

In 1629 Giovanni Battista Lalli, a man of letter originating from Norcia, wrote a poem dedicated to Roman Emperor Titus Vespasian, "Ruined Jerusalem". The Emperor's grand-mother, Vespasia Polla, was born from an aristocratic family whose roots were in ancient Norcia, and Lalli intended to celebrate the fame and deeds of a most illustrious offspring of his own land.

In depicting the ranks of soldiers which were supporting Titus in his successful effort to conquer Jerusalem in 70 A.D., Lalli portrays two generals, Leonzo and Fuscone, who had joined the Roman troops «from ancient Norcia with its snow-clad mountains» (in Italian: «di Norsia antica dal nevoso monte»). Leonzo, an elderly man, tells Titus that when he was young he had accompanied his grand-mother Vespasia to the cave of the Sibyl: she wanted to ask the oracle and learn about the fate and future fortune of his child grand-son, the Emperor-to-be Titus.

And here is the description of the Sibyl's cave, as put down by Lalli, who certainly had the occasion to see the real cavern as it appeared to visitors at the beginning of the seventeenth century:

«After having confronted with much effort, and conquered, the precipitous height of Mount Vettore, she [Vespasia Polla] reached the cavern which in its unfathomable bowels conceals the wise Woman. There opens the gloomy, awful mouth of that huge Sibyl's cave; and neither Sun ever breaks

in, nor transparent air, as horrible darkness alone rules there with its eternal night. Made of sheer iron is the heart of those who dare to get through, fearing not in their uncorrupted soul, for the cavern is guarded by Dragons and Panthers, and a hundred formidable Hydras and beasts».

Fig. 6 - A 1630 edition of "Ruined Jerusalem" with the excerpt on the Sibyl's cave

[in the original Italian poetic text:
«E di Vittor già superata, e vinta,
con sudor molto, la scoscesa altezza;
Peruenne à l'antro, che ne le profonde
Viscere sue, la saggia Donna asconde.
S'apre la bocca horribilmente oscura
Di quella immane Sibillina grotta;
Ove il Sol mai non entra, ò l'aria pura;
Ma 'l fosco horror perpetuamente annotta:
Ben hà di ferro il cor chi s'assicura

D'entrarvi, e da timor l'alma incorrotta;
Perch'in guardia di lei, Draghi e Pantere
Stanno, e cento Idre spaventose, e fere»]

Lalli's words are truly thrilling and full of emotional feeling: they are to be considered as a true description of the cave's appearance in the early seventeenth century. Lalli actually saw the cave's entrance, and the vision deeply impressed upon his soul.

At that time, the cave was dark and cold and deep and frightful: a sight that was not easily forgotten, and a further good reason for the cavern's sinister renown among travellers coming from all over Europe.

7. Excavating the Sibyl's cave

In modern times, the Sibyl's cave could be seen by visitors as a sealed hollow, sitting on its deserted mountain-top. In 1885, Giovambattista Miliani, a member of the family who founded an historical paper factory in Fabriano, on the eastern side of the Apennines, and himself an enthusiastic hiker, pushed himself up to the top of Mount Sibyl, having been lured there, as many others in earlier times, by the enthralling call raised by the ancient legend.

What he found up there was a mere «heap of wrecked stones». No trace of the cave's entrance was to be seen. The access to the Sibyl's kingdom was permanently sealed, buried forever under a solid mound of rocks.

But why the cave on the Sibyl's mountain-top has never been excavated?

Actually it was.

The first in a series of modern excavation campaigns began in 1920, following a wave of fresh attention for the cavern due to an increasing scrutiny of the legend's roots and historical links carried out by a number of scientists and philologists. A special committee was set up in Montemonaco, a small hamlet sitting just below the Sibyl's cliff: a

«Committee for the excavation of Mount Sibyl's cavern» promoted by Mario Monti Guarnieri.

The excavations were effected in August, supported by good weather and clear sky. And the initial results were absolutely encouraging: indeed, a section of the cave's entrance was unearthed, «shallow and a few yards long, an uncomfortable passageway to be accessed by twisting one's body inside it. A recess of the cave goes markedly down and it seems it might be the initial portion of a passageway sloping down like a staircase towards a further hollow, with the first cave being a sort of anteroom to that subsequent cavity. Yet the latter is presently filled up with stones, both small and large».

Fig. 7 - Mount Sibyl, excavations on the peak in 1920

The excavations proceeded tirelessly on the Sibyl's crowned mountain-top. The men worked with enthusiasm at the cave's entrance by the pick and shovel, in hopes of breaking into the inner recesses of the cavern. At the time, the gaping mouth of the cave was still visible: a dark hollow under the ruthless sunlight which flooded the cliff at midday, a condition almost unbearable for the people who were engaged in the daring expedition.

And yet, only a few years later - when the Committee would gain the support of important members of the Italian Fascist party for a new round of excavations - the entrance to the cave will prove to have vanished once more amid the rubble and broken stones: unknown treasure hunters had attempted unsuccessfully at breaking into the cave, causing additional destruction and damaging the outer hollow irreparably.

And that was just the beginning.

8. The Apennine Sibyl under Fascist rule in Italy: Giuseppe Moretti

Italians have never attained the degree of wicked folly reached by German Nazis, who were utterly and morbidly fascinated by the occult and the esoteric; nevertheless, the captivating power of the Apennine Sibyl's legend was so strong that it appears to have bewitched - though for far more positive scientific and cultural reasons - a prominent member of the Italian Fascist administration in 1920s: Giuseppe Moretti.

Moretti was a gifted, professional archeologist who was bestowed the highest honours during the Fascist rule in Italy, as he was appointed the Director General at the Department of Antiquities and Heritage of Latium and head of the National Roman Museum. In 1937, he was entrusted the difficult task to carry out the complex excavations in central Rome during which the most valuable fragments of Augustus' Ara Pacis (see picture) were unearthed, restored and positioned in a different location along the Tiber's bank, where we can still see them in present days.

Fig. 8 - Giuseppe Moretti (right) with a frieze just unburied in Rome and belonging to the Ara Pacis

Before taking his high post in Rome, Moretti had been the head of the Department of Antiquities in the local areas of Marche and Abruzzi. In addition to that, he was born in the Marche region: he had lived his childhood in San Severino Marche - at the very door of the Sibillini Mountain Range - he knew the Sibyl's legend at heart, and his soul could not avoid the centuries-old spell that trickled out from the gloomy cave opening on the mountain-top.

So in 1926, when Italian Senator Pio Rajna - the philologist who was equally fascinated by the same ancient legend - proposed to him a new excavation campaign at the cave, he had no hesitation: picks and spades were carried up to the cliff of Mount Sibyl once more (see picture), this time under public administration control. Results came in very quickly: preliminary probing proved that an underground hollow was actually present, and the explorers were able to creep into it «through a narrow crack which is to be found within the slanting layers of rock». However, the

subterranean cavity was «less than twenty-five feet long, thirteen feet wide and ten feet high», with no further access «to any internal vaults, galleries or pits. This vestibule alone presents itself free from the rubble».

The hidden magic was at work again, as in past centuries: men were on the mountain-top, as contemporary knights, in search of the hidden realm of the Sibyl. But the prophetess wouldn't let her secret be uncovered easily. And Giuseppe Moretti, a passionate, skilled scientist couldn't do more than write the following lines in his official campaigning report: «a small opening only, from that same vestibule, betokens the possible existence, in a long-gone past or maybe even in present times, not really of the actual chambers that popular lore had turned into the Queen Sibyl's paradise, but at least of further hollows that might be placed beyond the entrance cavity».

The dream could not be brought into the real world. The cave still resisted any efforts to break in. Queen Sibyl was still concealed under layers and layers of rock. But the heart of men had made a further attempt at unveiling the mystery: a trail of endeavours that is rooted into antique past and still continues today.

9. Diggers at the Sibyl's cave: an account by Fernand Desonay

Belgian philologist Fernand Desonay took part in various excavation campaigns on the Sibyl's mountain-top. In 1930 he wrote a thrilling firsthand report on the digging activity carried out on the cliff. Here is what he found there:

«The subsequent year I had the chance to pay a second, more rewarding visit to the cave set amid the Apennines, together with a few of my Italian friends, between 15 and 18 August 1930. Our small party left Norcia on the morning of August, 15th. The next day, we reached a shepherd's bivouac at 5.400 feet on the mountain. On August 17th, we attained the cavern, at eight in the morning. What a remarkable peace around the Sibyl's peak, in the vicinity of the paradise!...

The cave had been turned thoroughly upside down. Recent excavation works had utterly changed its outward aspect. The underground cavity had completely disappeared. We could see some heaps of fragmented rocks. The clumsy diggers, considering the hard exertion they had undergone, might even have achieved a minimal result, had they followed with more resolute confidence the marks of the ancient hollow rather than digging in the wrong direction. A huge boulder of rock, once rolled before the cave's entrance by superstitious shepherds, now was set free altogether; its appearance was not that of a stone formerly in place.

My friends and I began to clear the ground around the large boulder. And soon, down and on the left side, we uncovered the underground hollow...»

Fig. 9 - The account written by Fernand Desonay on the excavations carried out on Mount Sibyl in 1930

[in the original French text: «L'année suivante, j'eus l'occasion de faire, en compagnie de quelques amis italiens, entre le 15 et le 18 août 1930, une seconde visite, plus fructueuse, à la grotte de l'Apennin. Notre petite troupe avait quitté Norcia dans la matinée du 15 août. Le 16, nous nous trouvions dans un campement de bergers, à l'altitude de 1800 mètres. Le 19 [erroné pour le 17 - note du rédacteur] au matin, nous attegnions la grotte, vers le 8 heures. Quelle paix autour de la Sibylle, dans le voisinage du paradis!... La caverne était sens dessus dessous. De récents travaux d'exploration en avaient complètement modifié l'habitus. Masquée l'ouverture du souterrain. On distinguait quelques amas de pierres gluantes. Les fouilleurs inexpérimentés, vu la peine qu'ils s'étaient donnée, auraient peut-être réussi à découvrir quelque chose si, au lieu de prendre une mauvaise direction, ils

avaient suivi avec plus de confiance le tracé de l'antique terrier. Un gros quartier de roche, que des bergers superstitieux avaient fait rouler autrefois devant l'ouverture, se trouvait complètement mis à nu; son aspect n'était pas celui d'une pierre de rapport. Mes compagnon et moi, nous commençâmes à déblayer le terreau tout autour de la grosse pierre. Et bientôt, en bas, vers la gauche, nous découvrîmes le souterrain....»]

Let's continue with the description he provided as to the small 1930 expedition:

«... And soon, down and on the left side, we uncovered the underground hollow. After efforts lasting an hour , we had carved an aperture some three feet deep. The chasm gaped towards the inner portion of the cave. I myself, using a torchlight, distinctly saw, at the very bottom of our excavation, an abyss. A member of our party also thought he could feel a faint whiff of air coming out from the inside. Just an illusion?... Yet the person who felt that is used to this kind of works.

To gain a better insight into the actual situation, we tried to attach a stone to the far end of a rope: our intention was to hurl the stone into the void so as to ascertain the depth of the abyss. A first rock was not heavy enough to stretch the rope. A second one, of more remarkable size, did not fit into the hole; we pushed it in place, hoping we would win the opposition of the ground nearby: unfortunately enough, the rock got stuck in the gaping void, and we weren't able to set it free... owing to the lack of any effective tool, we had to make up our minds that our efforts were all in vain, and that we had to abandon our excavations. As a result, in low spirits and with pensive attitudes, we retraced our steps to the valley».

Fig. 10 - The account written by Fernand Desonay (right) on the excavations carried out on Mount Sibyl in 1930

Despite the unsuccessful attempt, Fernand Desonay would have a new chance to explore the mystery of the Sibyl. That will occur twenty-three years later, when he will reach the mountain-top once again, together with Mr. Annibaldi and his well-equipped team.

[in the original French text: «Et bientôt, en bas, vers la gauche, nous découvrimés le souterrain. Après une heure d'efforts, nous avons pratiqué une ouverture profonde d'environ deux mètres. Le vide béait vers l'intérieur. Moi même, m'aidant d'une torche, j'aperçus distinctement, tout au fond de notre excavation, le gouffre. Un d'entre nous crut même déceler un léger courant d'air en provenance de l'intérieur. Illusion?... Pourtant, celui qui affirmait ce détail a l'habitude des travaux de l'espèce.

Afin de mieux nous rendre compte de la réalité, nous songeâmes à lier une pierre à l'extrémité d'une corde: notre intention était de pousser cette pierre dans le vide, pour mesurer la profondeur du gouffre. Une première pierre n'était pas assez pesante pour tendre la sonde. Une seconde, de dimensions plus respectables, n'entraît pas bien; nous la poussâmes, croyant vaincre la

résistance du terreau tout autour: hélas! elle s'encastra dans le boyau, et il ne nous fut possible de la faire bouger... Vu la manque d'instruments idoines, il nous fallut bien nous convaincre de l'inutilité de nos efforts, abandonner les fouilles. Et c'est pourquoi, un peu mélancoliques, nous reprîmes, bredouilles, le chemin du retour.»]

10. Diggers at the Sibyl's cave: 1953 excavations

Following two passionate speeches on the Apennine Sibyl's legend delivered by Fernand Desonay in Rome at the beginning of 1953, a new official digging expedition moved to the Sibillini Range in the summer of that same year. It was led by Giovanni Annibaldi, the Director General of the Department of Antiquities of Marche, and included Fernand Desonay and Domenico Falzetti as team members.

It was no small party: there were «workers, forest rangers, firefighter, equipped with all the essential devices», as reported in a description by René Herval, “From Mount Sibyl in Italy to the German Venusberg”.

«They ascertained that the cavern had been possibly shaken by the earthquake that hit the region on 1st December 1328», added Mr. Herval, «and that the inner part was in consequence obstructed by the collapsed boulders and debris. At a depth of some eighteen feet, they found beneath the rubble a Tournois coin of Henry II, a spur and a knife. This trove should point to the fact that the cave still accommodated visitors a century and a half after Antoine de La Sale's excursion».

Fig. 11 - 1953 excavations on the Sibyl's mountain-top

«Owing to the obstruction caused by the ancient subsidence which prevented further investigation, the 1953 team had to give up and withdraw [as it had already happened in 1930]; yet this first deep probing activity had resulted in the detection of extended subterranean hollows.»

As ever, the Sibyl eluded any attempts to break into her cave and unveil her long-preserved secret.

Fig. 12 - 1953 excavations on the Sibyll's mountain-top

[in the original French text: «La dernière en date des tentatives faites pour scruter les mystères de la Sibylle fut réalisée en 1953 sous la direction du surintendant des Archives des Marches, le professeur Giovanni Annibaldi, accompagné d'ouvriers, de gardes forestiers et de pompiers, munis du matériel indispensable. On constata alors que la grotte avait dû être ébranlée par le tremblement de terre du 1er décembre 1328 et que l'intérieur en était, de ce fait, obstrué par les blocs de pierre et les gravats. A six mètres de profondeur environ, on découvrit sous les décombres un sol tournois de Henri II, un éperon et un couteau: ceci indiquerait que la grotte recevait encore des visiteurs un siècle et demi après le passage d'Antoine de la Salle. En présence de l'obstacle opposé aux investigations par les anciens éboulements, l'équipe de 1953 dut battre à son tour en retraite, mais ce premier sondage profond avait permis de constater qu'on se trouvait en présence d'immenses souterrains.»]

11. Confronting the Sibyl: modern technology vs. antique spell

In the fall of 2000, an expedition carrying a bulky machinery ascended the Sibyl's mountain-top. They were determined to challenge the ancient prophetess with the most advanced technology: the georadar analysis.

«The zone is not very large», they wrote in a scientific paper by D. Aringoli, B. Gentili, G. Pambianchi and A. M. Piscitelli, «it is encircled by precipices, and it lies on a very steep slope, which is difficult to reach». They were forced to discard the classical seismic method (disruptive to an excessive degree) and selected the georadar analysis, which offered the additional advantage of an «easy transportation of equipment to the site».

They positioned the device at many spots along a predetermined grid on the cliff of Mount Sibyl (see figure), and shot ground-penetrating microwave radio pulses at the Sibyl's rocky surface. In this way they covered some 9 linear kilometers just around the cave's collapsed entrance.

Fig. 13 - Mount Sibyl, the diagram of the survey completed on the cliff in year 2000

The results were amazing (see figure). The echoing pulses, as reflected by the subterranean structures, «clearly individuate a fracture in the underground», they reported, «stretching roughly in a direction E-W and emerging southwards». There were «horizontal and vertical hollows, with an average width of about 2 metres (going up to a width of 8 m), located at varying depths of between those of 10 and 14 metres». The horizontal development of the hidden cavities reached «a maximum size of about 300 m, with galleries a few meters in diameter, located at different depths».

Fig. 14 - Mount Sibyl in a 3-D diagram based on the reflected georadar signals

Was the Apennine Sibyl about to surrender and deliver all of her secrets? The answer - unfortunately - was no: as the scientists wrote in their paper, published in 2007 by the Geological Society of London, the subsequent investigative phase, which would imply the drilling of probing holes on the mountain-top, «has been unexplainably prohibited by a veto of the Sibillini Mountain National Park Office and of other local institutions».

And the secrets of the Sibyl remain veiled.

12. The Sibyl's cave, today

Today, the Sibyl's cave rests at the bottom of a shallow hollow, lying on the versant looking towards the south side of the peak. The grassy ground, departing from its usual, barren roughness, gives way to a sort of trench, excavated by all appearances in the very rock of the cliff; it is full of rubble and large broken stones, definitely the offspring of the shattering of the same rocky material of which the mount itself is made. Scaffolding tubes cover with rust, portions of wooden beams, fragments of rotten planks still emerge from the jumble of beaten and disfigured boulders, attesting by their miserable wretchedness to the unsuccessful, devastating attempts at breaking into the cavern by force.

Fig. 15 - The Sibyl's cave as it appears today

Thus, this is what remains today of the famous cave of the Sibyl. A mystery which is still unsolved.

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